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The Main Factors for the Degradation of Pastures in the Disposal of Forestry

Karomatov Valikhon Shabobo ugli

Assistant, “Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” National Research University

Rakhimov Khamidjon Orif ugli

Master, “Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers” National Research University

Annotation: *In the article scientific and practical work on the prevention and effective use of degradation of forestry in pasture lands, its organization. Data and recommendations are presented on project methods for the use of pasture land in climate change conditions.*

Key words: *mountain, desert, meadow, degradation, land, agricultural land, climate, forestry.*

Introduction. It is known that the impact of climate change on agriculture in the world has bad consequences. The Land Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the categories of agricultural land is 20761.6 thousand hectares of the total land area of respublka (i.e. 44892.4 thousand hectares) [1-3]. This means that our agricultural land accounts for 46.08% of the Republic in total. Current cases of erosion, degradation-inducing factors, anthropogenic factors are adversely affecting agricultural land, increasing year-on-year, on arable land, chalk land, gardens, pasture and hay-covered land [4-6]. It is a narrow fact that the air warms up from year to year, there is little precipitation, the lack of water on some cultivated lands is not only in us, but it also becomes a global problem. The development of livestock first of all, the increasing demand of the population for meat and dairy products will further increase the use of pasture land. The pasture and hay fields occupied in agriculture cover 21,102.5 thousand hectares (43% of the total agricultural land area). Of this, 17,415,000 hectares are located in the desert region, and 3,687,000 in the mountain and mountain regions. 3,282,000 hectares of pasture and hay were allocated to forest farms with the right to permanent use, 194,000 hectares with the right to permanent use for industrial and defense purposes, and 9,393,000 hectares on lease to agricultural enterprises [7-9]. The remaining 8,233,000 hectares, of which 1,635,000 hectares, are without temporary distribution, while 6,598,000 hectares remain unused in the state reserve for years [10-12].

In pasture and hay fields, cases of erosion occur on pasture lands and degradation occurs on pasture lands as a result of current overgrazing of livestock and grazing of livestock are observed year after year [13-15].

Geobotany monitoring work has been observed to reduce grazing areas by 16.4 million hectares (78 percent) in crisis, and 20 percent by the present time the number of pasture and hay plants and species in the country have decreased, and productivity has decreased by 2 times (Table 1).

Table 1 Distribution of pastures by Republic of Karakalpakstan and Regions (Cadastral Agency National Report 2015-2019 y.y.)

Name of Regions	Area (thousand, hectare) 2015 year	Area (thousand, hectare) 2016 year	Area (thousand, hectare) 2017 year	Area (thousand, hectare) 2018 year	Area (thousand, hectare) 2019 year	Area (thousand, hectare) 2020 yaer
Republic Of Karakalpakstan	5275,1	5277,5	5277,7	5278,4	5277,8	5175,6
Andijan region	21,3	21,2	21,2	21,2	21,0	21,1
Bukhara region	2543,2	2543,0	2541,3	2540,8	2530,4	2558,1
Jizzakh region	757,8	757,8	757,8	757,7	750,5	726,7
Kashkadarya region	1415,3	1408,4	1408,4	1407,3	1407,1	1406,8
Navoi region	8745,6	8745,3	8745,0	8737,7	8747,6	8762,3
Namangan region	152,4	152,4	151,4	151,2	151,1	150,8
Samarkand region	793,8	797,9	797,7	797,3	797,1	797,1
Surkhandarya region	830,9	830,9	830,8	830,3	826,7	826,5
Syrdarya region	20,5	20,4	20,3	20,2	20,3	20,5
Tashkent region	436,1	440,0	439,9	440,2	440,0	437,6
Fergana region	23,5	23,5	23,5	23,5	23,5	23,4
Khorezm region	110,1	110,1	109,4	109,4	109,4	109,3
Total	21125,6	21128,4	21124,4	21115,5	21102,5	21015,8

The results of the study and their discussion of pasture land design are a very important solution to the development of the livestock sector in our country. Farmers and landowners will be helped by a project map to the use of livestock and rotational pastures land, support a land use network that promotes soil quality and many practices that develop it, a solution to the direct elimination of the main educational, political, economic and social barriers to the reintegration of livestock.

According to the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 23, 2018 "On livestock measures to further improve the procedure for setting the boundaries of administrative-territorial units, correspondence of land resources and conducting geobotanical research in pastures and hayfields", geobotanical research is carried out in our Republic [16-18].

Based on Appendix 3 of this decision "conducting geobotanical research in pasture and hay fields" through The Republic of Uzbekistan conducted a geobotanical survey of 10.8 million hectares of pastures with vegetation cover and, analyzed by case, found that the degradation of pasture lands occurred in 1990, when 540,000 hectares of pasture lands were degraded.

In 2000, 11% of the area of 1.2 million hectares, in 2020, these rates increased by 19% - that is, cases of decline and disappearance of pasture plants were found, which were degraded in 2.0 million hectares of pasture land in total. If you are afraid to make an approximate book by 2030, then this scare is 30%, that is, 3.2 mln.ga pastures can forecast cases of degradation of our lands. The study conducted a survey of pasture lands in regions (Ohangaran and Bostanlik districts of Tashkent region, Forish and Zomin districts of Jizzakh region, Takhakopir and Moynok districts of Republic of Karakalpakhistan, Bukhara region, Nurota district of Navoi region, Boysun District of Surkhandarya region, Guzor and Mubarak districts of Kashkadarya region). In these areas, degraded pasture land area is 2.0 million hectares (i.e. 19% of the total pasture land area), good pasture land area is 2.6 million hectares (24%), medium pasture land area is 6.2 million hectares. The medicinal plants distributed in these pasture lands were identified as species number 21, 8 listed in the Red Book, 11 harmful and poisonous, and 53 pasture plant species that eat livestock. A fundamental assessment of the condition has been an important factor in establishing measures to restore or preserve areas with a worsening condition and degradation.

In **conclusion**, we would like to say that we will cite my following recommendations for improving the condition of pasture land and reducing degradation factors:

1. In order to preserve bio diversity, prevent degradation, geobotanical research every 5 years, monitoring every year and organizing training courses for pasture land users;
2. Re-establishment of pastures where pasture users are degraded from their accounts;
3. Current tax collection i.e. the introduction of a differentiated tax payment system to all grazing users, not just farm oxen.

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